

NOTES

Factors Influencing the Formation of Mixed Ligand Complexes of Neodymium(III)

D. N. SHELKE*

Department of Chemistry, Marathwada University,
Aurangabad-431 004

Manuscript received 21 June 1982, revised 16 May 1984,
accepted 10 August 1984

THERE has been a recent increase in interest of neodymium(III) chemistry due partially to an excellent review by Sigel¹ and partially to interesting properties of lanthanides which could substitute for calcium and produce an active enzyme system^{2,3}, particularly neodymium was better stimulator for the conversion of trypsinogen to trypsin than calcium ion⁴.

The binary and ternary complexes of neodymium ion with various ligands have been extensively studied⁵⁻⁹, while very little work seems to have been done in case of alkyl substituted malonic acids^{10,11}, and surprisingly nothing about the mixed-ligand complexes with thiodicarboxylic acids. In view of the remarkable differences in complexing abilities of the carboxylic and phenolic acids, we have reported previously the ternary complexes of neodymium(III) with substituted dicarboxylic, phenolic and pyridine carboxylic acids^{12,13}. Now we report here in addition to the few data of binary complexes already reported, the equilibrium studies on the mixed ligand complex formation occurring when neodymium(III) is mixed with methyl- and dimethylmalonic acids, and thiodicarboxylic and some substituted succinic acids.

Experimental

The ligands; thiodiacetic (acetic 2,2'-thio-bis, thiodiglycolic), thiodipropionic (propionic 3,3'-thio-bis), methylmalonic (methylpropanedioic), dimethylmalonic (dimethylpropanedioic), succinic (butanedioic), itaconic (methylenebutanedioic) and chlorosuccinic (chlorobutanedioic) acids of Fluka (Purum) and B.D.H. (AnalaR) were used as such. Hydrated metal salt of reagent quality was obtained from B.D.H. and the concentration of metal ion was estimated gravimetrically as Nd_2O_3 . Double-distilled water was used in the preparation of solutions. The details regarding other chemicals are described previously^{14,15}.

All pH measurements were carried out with an Elico L1-120 digital pH meter with glass and calomel electrodes having an accuracy of ± 0.01

pH unit at 30° and ionic strength 0.1 M (NaClO_4). The pH meter was standardised before each titration by a buffer solution of potassium hydrogen phthalate of pH value 4.01 at 30°.

Results and Discussion

Although reliable constants for the neodymium parent complexes of the methylmalonic and dimethylmalonic are not available in the literature, evaluation of formation constant necessitated the determination of these data at experimental conditions. Since stability constants of neodymium complexes of few ligands were determined earlier^{12,13}, the present work reports only the values obtained for the present complexes. Table I lists the data relating to the complexes of neodymium(III).

TABLE I—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF NEODYMIUM(III) COMPLEXES AT 30° AND $\mu=0.1$ M (NaClO_4)

Acids	K_{MX}^M / K_{MY}^M	K_{MY}^{MY}
Methylmalonic	5.33 (2)	2.91 (1)
Dimethylmalonic	4.95 (3)	2.68 (2)
Succinic	3.38 ^a	
Itaconic	3.77 ^a	
Chlorosuccinic	2.42 (2)	
Thiodiacetic	3.22 ^b	
Thiodipropionic	3.21 ^b	

* Standard deviations in parentheses.
^aRef. 12, ^bRef. 13

It is observed from the data (Table I) that the nature of coordinating atoms for the ligands are similar and tabulated stability constants are expected by their basicities, ring size and nature of the substituent in parent acid except dimethylmalonic acid. In fact, higher stability constants should have been obtained in dimethylmalonic than methylmalonic, contrary to this, destabilised nature of these binary bis-complexes are due to steric hindrance in dimethylmalonic acid, the presence of two methyl groups substituted to the same carbon atom to which carboxylate groups are bonded. In the case of thiodiacetic and thiodipropionic, the formation constants are almost the same. If the coordination occurs through S—O, the donor sulphur atom in such complexes confers the properties which are sometimes highly novel and differ markedly from those of the analogous oxygen derivatives. In extensive studies on neodymium(III) complexes with sulphur containing ligands^{16,17}, the formation constants are interpreted in terms of electrostatic repulsion indicating that the contribution due to π

* Department of Chemical Engineering, Jawaharlal Nehru Engineering College, Samarth Nagar, Aurangabad-431 001.

TABLE 2—COMPLEX FORMATION CONSTANTS FOR THE MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES OF Nd^{III}-METHYLMALONIC* AND -DIMETHYLMALONIC* WITH SUBSTITUTED SUCCINIC AND THIOACIDS** AT 30° AND μ=0.1 M (NaClO₄)

Acid/systems	β _{XY}	K _{DXY} ^a	K _{MX₂Y} ^{MX}	K _{MY₂X} ^{MY}	Δlog K
Methylmalonic-succinic	8.15 (4)	1.86	4.77	2.82	-0.56
Methylmalonic-itaconic	8.56 (2)	1.88	4.79	3.23	-0.54
Methylmalonic-chlorosuccinic	7.24 (3)	1.91	4.82	1.91	-0.51
Methylmalonic-thiodiacetic	8.02 (2)	1.89	4.80	2.69	-0.53
Methylmalonic-thiodipropionic	7.86 (3)	1.74	4.65	2.53	-0.68
Dimethylmalonic-succinic	7.78 (4)	1.72	4.40	2.45	-0.55
Dimethylmalonic-itaconic	8.11 (1)	1.66	4.34	2.78	-0.61
Dimethylmalonic-chlorosuccinic	6.80 (5)	1.70	4.38	1.47	-0.51
Dimethylmalonic-thiodiacetic	7.67 (3)	1.77	4.45	2.34	-0.50
Dimethylmalonic-thiodipropionic	7.38 (2)	1.49	4.17	2.05	-0.78

Standard deviations in parentheses.

^a for the reaction: MX + MY₂ ⇌ MXY + MY, * Ligand Y, ** Ligand X.

interaction in M-S bond is not significant. This effect is certainly reduced in neodymium complexes than uranyl¹⁸⁻²⁰.

The mixed ligand complexes were studied at a neodymium ion-ligand (X)-ligand (Y) ratio 1 : 1 : 1, under which condition formation of the species MX₂Y and MXY₂ can be neglected. The concentration of various species, H₂X, H₂Y, M, MX, MY, MY₂ and MXY and the different equilibrium constants were evaluated at TIFR Computer Centre, Bombay by the method of Ramamoorthy and Manning²¹ as outlined in our earlier papers^{14,15}. The corresponding data of neodymium(III) mixed ligand complexes of type MXY are given in Table 2.

The stabilisation constant, ΔlogK is the difference between measured values of stability constants which is defined by Sigel²²

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \log K &= \log K_{MX_2Y}^{MX} - \log K_{MY_2X}^{MY} \\ &= \log K_{MY_2X}^{MY} - \log K_{MX_2Y}^{MX} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The disproportionation or mixed constant K_{DXY} can be given by reactions (2) and (3).

Table 2 suggests that ΔlogK is negative and very close to -0.6 value expected on the basis of statistical considerations, indicating thereby the preferential formation of ternary complexes than the corresponding binary. K_{DXY} values point out that the formation *via* reaction (3) of the mixed ligand complexes containing methylmalonic and dimethylmalonic is determined.

The value K_{DXY} is clearly dependent on the stabilities of the binary bis-complexes and since these bis-complexes are not intermediates in the formation of the ternary complexes, the value of K_{DXY} may not truly reflect the stability of the mixed complex. However, K_{DXY} will tend to be less dependent than ΔlogK on differences in the charges of the ligand X and Y. Hence, the choice between using ΔlogK and K_{DXY} to give a measure of stabilisation of ternary complexes will depend on the particular comparison being made. The complex stability (ΔlogK) is constant, obtained from the subtraction of two equilibrium constants, and the observed values of ΔlogK are due to the lower values of binary bis-complexes, particularly in case of chlorosuccinic acid system. The slight differences present in the binary complexes are not suppressed in the ternary complexes. In addition to this, the steric hindrance in dimethylmalonic acid systems affects the stability of ternary complex and resulted into the lower values of ΔlogK, despite the two negative charges of the ligands X and Y.

It may be seen from Figs. 1 and 2 that, except thiodipropionic acid, the values of ΔlogK and K_{DXY} generally increase with decreasing the basicity of the secondary ligands. This may be explained by assuming the increased value of logK₁/K₂ in parent complexes, is predominantly a consequence of steric reasons. This means that the mixed ligand complex

Fig. 1. Relation between ΔlogK and pK_{H₂X}^H + pK_{HX}^H for mixed ligand complexes of (A) Nd(III)-methylmalonicdicarboxylic acids, and (B) Nd(III)-dimethylmalonicdicarboxylic acids. Acids: (1) succinic, (2) itaconic, (3) chlorosuccinic, (4) thiodiacetic, (5) thiodipropionic.

Fig. 2. Relation between K_{DXY} and $pK_{H_2X}^H + pK_{HX}^H$ for mixed ligand complexes of Nd^{III} -methylmalonidicarboxylic acids. Acids: (1) succinic, (2) itaconic, (3) chlorosuccinic, (4) thiodiacetic, (5) thiodipropionic.

formation occurs in accordance with the stability constants of the parent complex of ligand X. Contrary to this speculation, the higher value of $\log K_1/K_2$ at least in dimethylmalonic steric hindrance may influence the mixed ligand stabilities. Because of this reason, in plots of K_{DXY} against ligand basicity relating to the mixed ligand system of dimethylmalonic acid do not give straight line relationship between these two quantities.

It may be further established from Figs. 1 and 2 that more significant differences from the values determined for $\Delta \log K$ and K_{DXY} arise only for the various mixed ligand complexes of thiodipropionic acid (point 5). These differences, however, point to the effect resulting from the size of the chelate ring and from the specific nature of the donor atoms.

From the experimental data it is obvious that $\Delta \log K$ is most appropriate for the characterising the extra stabilisation of mixed ligand complexes^{2a}, which has a value close to -0.6 . The disproportionation or mixing constant is resulted from the differences in the stability constants of the parent complexes. On the basis of the data obtained it is further pointed out that the steric hindrance exhibited in binary bis-complexes is not significantly suppressed in ternary complexes of dimethylmalonic acid.

Acknowledgement

The financial support of U.G.C., New Delhi is gratefully acknowledged. The author is particularly indebted to Dr. Leela G. Pardeshi for useful discussions.

References

1. H. SIGEL, *Met. Ions Biol. Systems*, 1973, 2, 65; 1976, 5, 148, 250; 1976, 6, 273; 1979, 9, 66, 1320,

2. D. W. DAENALL and E. R. BIRNBAUM, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1970, 245, 6484.
3. D. W. DAENALL and E. R. BIRNBAUM, *Biochemistry*, 1973, 12, 3489.
4. D. W. DAENALL and E. R. BIRNBAUM, *Met. Ions Biol. Systems*, 1976, 6, 275.
5. H. S. RANA and J. P. TANDON, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1978, 259, 236.
6. H. S. RANA and J. P. TANDON, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, 39, 1391.
7. S. D. MAKHIJANI and S. P. SANGAL, *Ann. Chem.*, 1978, 68, 461; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 670; *Chem. Era*, 1978, 14, 387.
8. N. A. KOSTROMINA and L. B. NOVIKOVA, *Zh. Neorg. Khim.*, 1980, 25, 2104.
9. N. A. KOSTROMINA, N. A. TANANAKVA, L. B. NOVIKOVA and YU B. SHEVCHENKO, *Teor. Eksp. Khim.*, 1979, 15, 744.
10. N. A. KOSTROMINA, T. V. ZAKHAROV, T. V. TERNOVAYA and S. B. PIRKES, *Koord. Khim.*, 1978, 4, 1526.
11. T. V. ZAKHAROV, *Zh. Khim. Abstr.*, 1979, 7V, 57.
12. D. N. SHELKE and D. V. JAHAGIRDAR, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1976, 49, 2142.
13. D. N. SHELKE and D. V. JAHAGIRDAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 344.
14. D. N. SHELKE and D. V. JAHAGIRDAR, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1979, 41, 925, 929.
15. D. N. SHELKE, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1979, 32, L45.
16. H. S. RANA and J. P. TANDON, *Indian J. Chem. Sect. A*, 1980, 19, 279.
17. H. S. RANA and J. P. TANDON, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 297.
18. D. N. SHELKE and D. V. JAHAGIRDAR, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, 43, 174.
19. D. N. SHELKE and D. V. JAHAGIRDAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 596.
20. D. N. SHELKE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, 59, 833.
21. S. RAMAMOORTHY and P. G. MANNING, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1973, 34, 1977.
22. H. SIGEL, *Angew. Chem.*, 1975, 14, 394.

Mass and X-Ray Photoelectron Spectral Studies of Bis(Acetylacetonato)-nitrosylchromium(I)

R. C. MAURYA* and R. K. SHUKLA

Department of Chemistry, Atarra P. G. College, Atarra-210 201 and

M. R. MAURYA

Regional Engineering College, Kurukshetra-132 119

Manuscript received 17 December 1982, revised 1 March 1984, accepted 10 August 1984

IN continuation of our work¹ on the synthesis and characterisation of bis(acetylacetonato)nitrosylchromium(I), studies have now been extended to mass and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy of the compound.

Experimental

All chemicals were reagent grade. The mass spectrum was measured using Atlas-CH4 mass spectrometer at acceleration voltage 1500 V, and ionisation energy 70 eV. The complex is directly introduced into the ion chamber and heated to a